

Using 2D Gaussian Splatting in Diffusion Models

Archan Ghosh

Birla Institute of Technology and Science, Pilani

gharchan@gmail.com

Abstract

Diffusion models have achieved remarkable success in image synthesis but remain computationally expensive due to iterative denoising in high-dimensional pixel space. Latent Diffusion Models (LDMs) alleviate this cost through compressed neural representations, yet often sacrifice high-frequency spatial detail during latent compression. In this work, we introduce a diffusion framework based on 2D Gaussian Splatting, replacing dense pixel-space representations with structured Gaussian primitives. Our approach employs an encoder-diffusion-renderer pipeline, where input images are first mapped into a compact Gaussian latent space parameterized by spatial location, scale, opacity, and color attributes. Diffusion is then performed directly over these Gaussian latents, enabling efficient generation while preserving fine-grained spatial structure. The denoised Gaussian representations are subsequently rendered back into the image domain using differentiable splatting. By operating on compact geometric primitives rather than dense latent tensors, our framework significantly reduces computational overhead while maintaining visual fidelity.

1. Introduction

Generative Artificial Intelligence has advanced visual content creation, with diffusion models[11][7] producing highly realistic images. However, these models demand high computational resources. This requirement limits their use in lightweight and real-time applications. Gaussian Splatting[3] has recently emerged as an efficient representation for images and scenes. It models visual data using collections of 2D or 3D Gaussian primitives. This approach enables faster rendering with lower computational cost. This work explores the use of 2D Gaussian Splatting as an alternative or complementary input representation for diffusion based image generation. Instead of operating directly on image pixels, diffusion models are applied to Gaussian-based representations. The objective is to assess whether efficient image synthesis can be achieved while maintaining acceptable visual quality. This work addresses the above limitation by intro-

ducing Gaussian splatting as an intermediate representation for image generation. Instead of modeling individual pixels, localized pixel regions are represented using parameterized Gaussian primitives. These primitives are resolution agnostic. They allow the representation to scale with image size while keeping the number of learnable elements fixed, which improves computational efficiency. The proposed framework uses a sliding window formulation. In this setup, a predefined set of Gaussian splats corresponds to local pixel clusters. An encoder [17] network maps the input image to the parameters of these Gaussian primitives, including spatial location and appearance attributes. A lightweight and fully differentiable renderer reconstructs the image from the Gaussian representation. This enables both quantitative and qualitative evaluation of reconstruction fidelity. The splat-based representation then becomes the target space for a diffusion model. The diffusion process learns to generate and refine Gaussian parameters instead of raw pixel values. Each Gaussian splat models both the geometric structure and the color distribution of the underlying image content. The current implementation focuses on unconditional generation[9][16]. However, the proposed architecture remains compatible with conditional diffusion frameworks. It can be extended to include class labels or other conditioning signals commonly used in diffusion based image synthesis.

2. Related Work

Although 2D Gaussian Splatting has become popular over the past few years, it is still primarily used as a building block towards 3D Gaussian Networks. Multiple layers of 2D Gaussians are either stacked or combined in different ways to ensure the correctness of the 3D Generation. In Gaussian Billboards [24], the authors unify Gaussian primitives with traditional computer graphics billboards by introducing per-splat texture interpolation. This approach replaces uniform color distributions with spatially varying textures, enhancing high-frequency detail and scene sharpness while maintaining the robust optimization of splat-based representations. Similarly in [12] 2D Gaussian Splatting (2DGS) addresses the geometric inconsistencies of 3D primitives by collapsing volumes into oriented planar disks that intrinsically

model surfaces. By utilizing a perspective-correct rasterization process and ray-splat intersection, the method achieves noise-free, view-consistent geometry and high-fidelity surface reconstruction without sacrificing real-time rendering performance. [18] Uses 2D gaussian splatting as a means for image inpainting. It utilizes a DINOv2[19] based feature extraction and Unet to repaint the missing parts of the image while keeping proper coherence. DiffusionGS[2] introduces a single-stage 3D diffusion framework that directly generates 3D Gaussian point clouds, bypassing the multi-view inconsistency issues inherent in 2D diffusion priors. By employing a scene-object mixed training strategy, the model achieves robust, feedforward reconstruction for both object-centric and general scenes with significantly faster inference speeds than state-of-the-art methods.

3. Method

3.1. Working Principle

The proposed system relies on the interplay between a Gaussian Splat Encoder, a lightweight Renderer, and a UNet[21][25] based diffusion model. At a fixed resolution of 128×128 , a single batch of images presents a raw data load that appears trivial in isolation. However, scaling this to the iterative nature of diffusion models creates a substantial bottleneck in both memory and compute. Processing tens of thousands of pixels per image over many timesteps becomes challenging and hardware demanding. Consequently, our approach abandons dense pixel processing in favor of a latent representation. We map each image to a grid of Gaussian primitives, effectively compressing the data into a smaller, structured format. Each Gaussian acts as a container for local spatial and appearance data. This shift allows the diffusion model to learn a far more efficient, low-dimensional representation without sacrificing the spatial coherence required for high-quality generation.

3.2. Architecture

The proposed architecture is composed of three main components: an encoder, a differentiable renderer, and a diffusion model. The encoder transforms an input image into a compact, structured latent representation based on Gaussian splats, capturing both spatial and appearance information. A lightweight, fully differentiable renderer reconstructs images from this latent representation, enabling evaluation of reconstruction fidelity and stable gradient flow. This splat-based latent space then serves as the operating domain for a U-Net based diffusion model, which learns to generate and refine Gaussian parameters over multiple diffusion steps. Together, these components form an efficient and scalable framework for image generation that operates in latent space rather than directly on pixels.

3.2.1. Splat Encoder

Figure 1. Architectural Block Diagram of Splat Encoder

The Gaussian Splat Encoder maps an input RGB image of size 128×128 into a structured latent representation suitable for splat-based rendering and diffusion modeling. The encoder consists of a sequence of convolutional layers that progressively down sample the input from 128×128 to a 32×32 grid using strided convolutions. Two convolutional layers with stride 2 [22] reduce the spatial resolution while increasing feature dimensionality. A projection layer then outputs a fixed set of Gaussian parameters for each grid cell. At each grid location, the encoder predicts parameters for two Gaussian splats, resulting in 18 output channels per cell. These parameters represent offsets in the x and y directions, anisotropic scales, rotation, RGB color values, and opacity. Formally, the encoder transforms an input tensor of shape $(B, 3, 128, 128)$ into a latent splat grid of shape $(B, 18, 32, 32)$. This corresponds to 2,048 Gaussian splats per image ($32 \times 32 \times 2$). The resulting representation provides a compact and resolution-aware description of image content that can be efficiently rendered or modeled by a downstream diffusion process. To improve representational capacity, an upgraded encoder variant has been later introduced. While the overall down sampling factor remains unchanged, this version increases feature depth and adds refinement layers at the 32×32 resolution. Instance normalization and LeakyReLU[26] activations are used throughout the network to improve training stability and feature consistency. After the initial strided convolutions reduce the input resolution from 128×128 to 32×32 , two additional convolutional layers operate at the same spatial resolution to refine local features without further down sampling. A final 1×1 convolution projects the refined features to the Gaussian parameter space. In this configuration, the encoder predicts parameters for four Gaussian splats per grid cell, resulting in 36 output channels. The output tensor has shape $(B, 36, 32, 32)$, corresponding to 4,096 Gaussian splats per image. This higher-capacity representation allows finer modeling of local structure and appearance while remaining significantly more compact than pixel-space representations. Showcased further

in B, 14

3.2.2. Splat Renderer

Figure 2. Architectural Block Diagram of Splat Renderer

The Differentiable Splat Renderer[14] reconstructs an image from the latent Gaussian splat representation by explicitly evaluating and compositing 2D anisotropic Gaussians in image space. Given a splat grid of shape $(B, C, 32, 32)$, the renderer reshapes this grid into a set of Gaussian primitives, resulting in $32 \times 32 \times 2 = 2,048$ splats per image. Each splat is parameterized by its center location, anisotropic scale, rotation angle, RGB color, and opacity. Splat centers are computed by combining fixed grid locations in normalized image coordinates with learned offsets. These offsets are constrained using a hyperbolic tangent function. Gaussian scales are enforced to be positive through an exponential transformation. Rendering is performed in a fully differentiable manner by evaluating each Gaussian over the image plane. To control computational cost, the image is processed in tiles of size 32×32 pixels. For each tile, the renderer computes the Gaussian contribution at every pixel using a quadratic form derived from the inverse covariance matrix. This formulation accounts for both anisotropic scaling and rotation. Each splat contribution is weighted by its opacity, and pixel colors are computed using a normalized weighted sum of splat colors. The rendered pixel value is given by:

$$I(x, y) = \frac{\sum_i w_i(x, y) \alpha_i c_i}{\sum_i w_i(x, y) \alpha_i + \epsilon} \quad (1)$$

where $w_i(x, y)$ denotes the Gaussian weight, α_i the opacity, and c_i the RGB color of the i 'th splat. By avoiding discrete rasterization and relying solely on tensor operations, the renderer remains fully differentiable, enabling end-to-end training with gradient-based optimization. The renderer is extended to support a higher-capacity splat representation with four Gaussian splats per grid cell. The overall rendering strategy remains unchanged, but the number of splats increases to match the upgraded encoder output. As a result, the renderer

now operates on 4,096 Gaussian splats per image. Grid-aligned base coordinates are computed in normalized image space and shared across splats within each cell. Learned offsets are scaled relative to the grid stride, allowing splat centers to shift locally while remaining spatially constrained. Gaussian scales are initialized with smaller values to promote denser local coverage, while colors and opacities are bounded using sigmoid activations to ensure stable rendering behavior. Gaussian evaluation is fully vectorized within each tile. The quadratic form is computed using explicit cosine and sine terms derived from the predicted rotation angles, enabling accurate modeling of anisotropic and rotated splats. Opacity-weighted Gaussian responses are accumulated across splats, and pixel colors are obtained through normalized blending. This updated renderer preserves full differentiability while supporting increased representational capacity, enabling higher-fidelity reconstruction and more expressive diffusion-based generation. 18 portrays how splats give rise to shape and colors.

3.2.3. U-Net Based Diffusion Model

Figure 3. Architectural Block Diagram of Diffusion U-Net

The diffusion component of the proposed framework is implemented using a U-Net based architecture[21] that operates directly on the latent[9] Gaussian splat representation. The network takes as input a tensor of shape $(B, 18, 32, 32)$, corresponding to number of Gaussian splats per grid cell with nine parameters each, and predicts denoised splat pa-

rameters at each diffusion timestep. The architecture follows an encoder-decoder structure with symmetric down sampling and up sampling paths connected through skip connections[10] to preserve spatial detail. Feature extraction begins with a convolutional projection into a 64-channel feature space. This is followed by two down sampling stages that reduce spatial resolution while increasing channel capacity to 128 and 256, respectively. Each stage uses residual blocks with group normalization and SiLU activations, supporting stable gradient flow and improved representational capacity. Temporal conditioning is introduced through a learned time embedding. The diffusion timestep is normalized and passed through a multilayer perceptron, and the resulting embedding is injected into each residual block through additive modulation. This allows the network to adapt its predictions based on the current diffusion step. The design follows standard diffusion modeling practices while remaining computationally efficient due to the reduced spatial resolution of the splat grid. The bottleneck consists of stacked residual blocks operating at the lowest spatial resolution. The decoder path then up samples the features back to the original grid size using nearest-neighbor interpolation and convolutional refinement. Skip connections from the encoder are fused through channel-wise concatenation and projection layers, ensuring that fine-grained spatial information is retained during reconstruction. 17 showcases the comparison of a generated image and its ground truth. The network outputs a tensor matching the input dimensionality, representing predicted Gaussian splat parameters. A hyperbolic tangent activation bounds the output values to the range $[-1, 1]$, preventing numerical instability and parameter explosion during diffusion training. This bounded formulation is particularly important for continuous splat attributes such as offsets, scales, color, and opacity. Overall, this U-Net architecture enables efficient diffusion modeling in a compact and structured latent space. Compared to pixel-space diffusion, it significantly reduces computational cost while preserving spatial coherence and expressive power. In 16 we have tried to show how the latent space looks like for a generated image for all the parameters of the Splat. Each resolution stage employs residual blocks with explicit time-dependent modulation. The time embedding is generated by normalizing the diffusion timestep and passing it through a two-layer multilayer perceptron. This embedding is added to feature maps within each residual block[10], enabling consistent conditioning across all network depths. Group normalization and SiLU[8] activations are used throughout the network to maintain training stability. The bottleneck includes a self-attention[23] module operating at the lowest spatial resolution. This allows the model to capture long-range dependencies across the splat grid, complementing the local receptive fields of convolutional layers. The attention output is further processed by residual blocks before enter-

ing the decoder. During up sampling, features are resized using nearest-neighbor interpolation and refined through convolutional layers. Skip connections from the encoder are concatenated with decoder features and projected using 1×1 convolutions before residual processing. This design ensures efficient feature fusion while controlling channel growth. The final output layer maps the features back to the splat parameter space, with a hyperbolic tangent activation applied to bound predictions and maintain numerical stability during diffusion. 15 Captures the fidelity of the diffusion process.

Figure 4. Block Diagram for Residual Block

Residual Blocks

Residual blocks[10] are used throughout the U-Net[21] to improve training stability and feature learning. Instead of learning a full transformation from scratch, each block learns a residual update that is added to its input. This skip connection helps gradients[20] flow more easily through deep layers and reduces the risk of vanishing gradients[20] during long training runs. In this model, each residual block includes normalization, non-linear activation, and convolutional layers, along with time-step conditioning from the diffusion process. The time embedding is added to the intermediate features, allowing the block to adapt its behavior depending on the current diffusion step. As a result, residual blocks help the network refine features progressively while maintaining stable optimization.

Figure 5. Block Diagram for Attention Block

Self-Attention Blocks

A self-attention layer[23] is included at the bottleneck of the U-Net to capture long-range dependencies within the latent splat grid. Convolutional layers are effective at modeling local structure, but they have limited ability to directly relate distant spatial regions. Self-attention addresses this by allowing each spatial location to interact with all other locations in the feature map. In the proposed model, multi-head self-attention[5] operates on the flattened spatial features and is followed by a small feedforward network. Residual connections are also used within the attention block to maintain stable gradients[20]. This mechanism helps the diffusion model learn global structure, such as overall shape

and spatial coherence, which is important when generating consistent splat-based image representations.

4. Experimentation

4.1. Dataset

All training is conducted using the STL 10 dataset[4]. To ensure a focused analysis, we restrict the input to the "Airplanes" class, creating a purely unconditional generation task. The data is pre-processed by normalizing and resizing images to 128×128 . This simplifies our evaluation, allowing us to judge the proposed architecture on its core merits namely, how well it handles reconstruction and generation rather than its ability to juggle diverse semantic labels.

4.2. Gaussian Splat Encoder Training

The Gaussian Splat Encoder is trained jointly with the differentiable renderer in an autoencoder-style[1] setup. The objective of this stage is to learn a stable and compact splat-based representation that can accurately reconstruct input images. Only the encoder parameters are optimized, while the renderer remains fixed and fully differentiable. Training is performed using images from the Airplanes class of the STL-10 dataset[4]. We use a batch size of 4, but to achieve a larger effective batch size, gradient accumulation is done. Gradients are accumulated over four iterations before performing an optimizer step, resulting in an effective batch size of 16. This improves gradient stability without increasing GPU memory usage. All input images are resized to a fixed resolution of 128×128 before being passed to the encoder. The encoder maps each image to a Gaussian splat grid, which is then rendered back into pixel space using the differentiable splat renderer. The reconstructed image is directly compared with the input image to compute the reconstruction loss. Training is carried out for a total of 150 epochs and follows a two-phase learning strategy. During the first phase, a higher learning rate is used to encourage rapid learning of coarse spatial structure and global appearance. After 50 epochs, the learning rate is reduced to allow finer detail refinement and improved convergence. This staged schedule helps balance fast initial learning with stable late-stage optimization. The encoder is optimized using the Adam optimizer[15]. The reconstruction objective combines a perceptual loss component with a pixel-wise error term. The perceptual loss is weighted more heavily to emphasize structural and semantic similarity, while the pixel-wise loss helps stabilize training and preserve low-level details. The formulation of this loss is discussed in detail in the following section. Throughout training, periodic qualitative evaluations are performed by visualizing reconstructed images alongside their corresponding inputs. These visual checks help verify training stability and confirm that the learned splat representations preserve both global structure and local details. This training stage

produces an encoder capable of generating consistent and expressive Gaussian splat representations. These representations serve as the foundation for subsequent diffusion-based modeling.

4.2.1. Loss Function used For Encoder Training

The Gaussian Splat Encoder is trained using a reconstruction-based objective that combines perceptual and pixel-level losses. The goal of this loss formulation is to encourage reconstructions that are not only close to the input images in a numerical sense, but also similar in visual structure and appearance. A perceptual loss based on a pretrained VGG-16[22] network is used as the primary supervision signal. Only the feature extraction layers of the network are retained, and all parameters are frozen during training. The reconstructed image and the target image are first normalized using ImageNet[6] statistics before being passed through the network. Feature activations are extracted from multiple intermediate layers corresponding to early and mid-level representations. These layers capture edges, textures, and coarse structures at different spatial scales. The perceptual loss is computed as the sum of mean squared errors between corresponding feature maps of the reconstructed and target images. By operating in feature space rather than pixel space, this loss emphasizes structural similarity and perceptual coherence. It reduces sensitivity to small pixel-level misalignments that are less important for visual quality, especially when modeling images using continuous Gaussian primitives. In addition to the perceptual loss, a pixel-wise mean squared error loss is applied directly in image space. This term provides low-level supervision and helps stabilize training by penalizing large deviations in color and intensity values. While perceptual loss guides global structure and texture, the pixel-level loss ensures basic fidelity to the input image. The final reconstruction loss is defined as a weighted combination of these two terms. The perceptual loss is assigned a higher weight, while the pixel-wise loss contributes a smaller stabilizing component. This weighting reflects the importance of preserving visual structure over exact pixel correspondence in the splat-based representation. During training, the combined loss is used to update only the encoder parameters. Gradients are accumulated over multiple iterations to support a larger effective batch size. This loss formulation plays a critical role in learning stable and expressive Gaussian splat parameters that can be efficiently rendered and later modeled by the diffusion network.

4.2.2. Encoder Training Results

Figure 6. Loss Curve of Encoder Training

The encoder shows steady and stable convergence throughout training. The loss drops sharply in the early epochs, falling from 10.77 to below 3 within the first ten epochs. This phase reflects rapid learning of coarse structure, overall shape, and dominant colors. From epochs 10 to 50, the loss continues to decrease more gradually. Improvements during this stage correspond to refinement of edges, textures, and local appearance. Small fluctuations are visible, which are expected when using perceptual supervision, but the overall trend remains consistently downward. After epoch 50, the learning rate is reduced for a polishing phase. This change leads to a smoother and more stable decline in loss. The model shifts from coarse reconstruction to fine detail refinement. The loss steadily decreases from around 1.26 to below 0.90 by the end of training.

In the final epochs, the curve begins to plateau with only minor improvements. This indicates that the encoder has largely converged and is producing stable splat representations. Overall, the training behavior confirms effective learning, stable optimization, and progressive improvement in reconstruction quality. Below are images that were decoded from Gaussian encoding to make sure visual fidelity is being correctly embedded.

Figure 7. Sample Images taken during training

4.3. Diffusion Model Training

The diffusion model is trained to operate directly on the Gaussian splat latent space produced by the encoder. Instead of pixel values, the network learns to model structured splat parameters arranged in a 32×32 grid with 36 channels. This significantly reduces spatial dimensionality while preserving meaningful image structure. A standard forward diffusion process is defined using a linear noise schedule. The noise variance increases gradually from a small value to a larger one across a fixed number of diffusion steps. At each training iteration, a random timestep is sampled, and Gaussian noise is added to the clean latent representation according to the precomputed noise schedule. This produces a noisy latent input that the network must denoise.[11] Before noise is added, the latent splat parameters are normalized using global minimum and maximum statistics computed over the dataset. The values are scaled to the range $[-1, 1]$ to ensure stable learning and consistent numerical behavior across training. This normalization is critical because the splat parameters have different natural ranges, and unbounded values can lead to unstable gradients. The diffusion network receives the noisy latent tensor along with the corresponding timestep as input. Temporal information is injected through a learned time embedding inside the U-Net. The model predicts a cleaned version of the latent representation, and its parameters are updated using gradient-based optimization. The AdamW optimizer is used to improve generalization and maintain stable weight updates during long training runs. Training is performed over an extended number of epochs to allow the model to gradually learn the complex distribution of air-plane shaped splat configurations[4]. Checkpoints are saved at regular intervals to prevent loss of progress and to allow intermediate evaluation. The training process is designed to be resumable. Along with model and optimizer states, global normalization statistics are stored and restored when training continues. This ensures consistency in data scaling across different training phases. Periodic visual evaluations are also performed during training. At intervals, latent samples are generated using the diffusion model, rendered into image space using the Gaussian renderer, and visually inspected. These previews provide qualitative feedback on generative progress and help confirm that the model is learning coherent structure rather than noise patterns. Overall, the diffusion training procedure focuses on long, stable optimization in a normalized latent space. By combining structured splat representations with a standard diffusion framework, the model learns to generate compact and spatially meaningful image representations efficiently.

4.3.1. Loss Function Used for Diffusion Training

The diffusion model is trained using a reconstruction objective defined in the latent splat space. At each iteration, the network receives a noisy version of a clean latent grid

along with the corresponding diffusion timestep. Its task is to predict a denoised version of that latent representation. The loss is computed by directly comparing the predicted clean latent tensor with the original clean latent tensor. We use a modified version of Huber loss[13] for this comparison that suits the latent space. As a result, it provides stable gradients while being less sensitive to outliers than pure L2 loss. This is useful when modeling splat parameters, where occasional large deviations may occur during early training. The loss is applied uniformly across all splat parameters, including spatial offsets, scale values, rotation, color, and opacity. Since all parameters are normalized to the range $[-1, 1]$ before training, the loss operates on a consistent scale across different attributes. This helps prevent any single parameter type from dominating the optimization.

By minimizing this loss, the diffusion model learns to progressively remove noise from latent splat representations across timesteps. This enables the network to model the underlying distribution of valid Gaussian splat configurations that correspond to realistic airplane images.

Loss is defined as follows:

$$L = \frac{1}{|\Omega|} \sum_{i \in \Omega} w_i l_\delta(\hat{x}_i - x_i)$$

where Ω denotes the set of spatial locations, w_i is the spatial weighting factor, and \hat{x}_i and x_i represent the predicted and target latent values, respectively and l_δ represent the Huber penalty.

4.3.2. Diffusion Training Results

Figure 8. Loss Curve of Diffusion Training

The diffusion training showed a steady and consistent improvement over the full training duration. In the early phase, the loss decreased quickly from about 0.028 at the beginning to nearly 0.018 within the first few thousand epochs. This rapid drop indicates that the model was able to learn the general structure of valid Gaussian splat configurations early in training. As training progressed beyond this stage, the rate of improvement became more gradual. Between roughly 5,000 and 15,000 epochs, the loss continued to decline from

around 0.013 – 0.014 to close to 0.010 – 0.011. Small oscillations were observed during this period, which is expected due to the stochastic timestep sampling used in diffusion training. Despite these variations, the overall trend remained downward, showing consistent learning. In the later stages, improvements became more subtle. From around 20,000 epochs onward, the loss values mostly remained in the range of 0.010 to 0.009, indicating that the model had already captured the main characteristics of the latent splat distribution. Training during this phase focused on refining finer details of the denoising process. By the end of the 50,000 epoch schedule, the loss reached approximately 0.0084, which represents the lowest range observed during training. The smooth progression from 0.028 to 0.008 without divergence suggests stable optimization throughout the long training run. In-depth look at experimentation settings [A](#)

5. Observation

The experimental results [C](#) show that the proposed framework performs reliably across all components of the pipeline. The Gaussian Splat Encoder learns a stable and compact representation that preserves the essential structure of the input images. Reconstructions produced through the differentiable renderer maintain clear object shapes, consistent color regions, and recognizable fine details. This confirms that the splat-based latent space is expressive enough to describe meaningful visual content while remaining significantly more compact than pixel space. Training behavior further supports this observation. The encoder loss decreases steadily and converges without significant instability, indicating that the combination of perceptual and pixel-wise supervision is effective for learning structured splat parameters. Visual comparisons between original and reconstructed images show progressive improvement over training, with sharper edges and better color consistency in later epochs. The diffusion model also demonstrates stable and consistent learning. Over long training schedules, the model learns to denoise latent splat grids and generate coherent new samples. Generated outputs display structured object forms and plausible spatial layouts rather than random patterns. This suggests that the diffusion process successfully captures the distribution of valid Gaussian splat configurations corresponding to airplane images. Another important observation is the stability of training across extended runs. Despite the large number of epochs required for diffusion learning, the normalization strategy and network design prevent divergence or numerical issues. Checkpoint sampling during training shows gradual qualitative improvement, indicating that the model continues refining details even in later stages. Overall, the results validate the effectiveness of combining Gaussian splatting with diffusion modeling. The approach achieves efficient learning in a compact latent space while maintaining visually meaningful generation quality. These findings

support the core objective of the work, which is to reduce computational cost without sacrificing spatial coherence and perceptual fidelity.

Figure 9. Samples Images Over Epochs

The examples above illustrate the training progression over 50,000 epochs. In the early stage, around epoch 100, the generated outputs appear mostly as noise with no recognizable structure. By roughly 3,000 epochs, basic shapes begin to form. Around 9,000 epochs, the generated images start to show clearly identifiable airplane structures. Beyond this point, improvements become more gradual and focused on detail. The model begins to produce better shading, more coherent backgrounds, and occasional human-like figures that appear more structured within the scenes. By 40,000 epochs, the outputs display richer colors, clearer object boundaries, and finer visual details, including small text-like patterns that appear more structured and legible. Post-training analysis C, 19

6. Conclusion

The study explored the use of 2D Gaussian splatting as a structured latent space for diffusion-based image generation. The results indicate that moving away from direct pixel-space modeling can still produce meaningful and visually coherent images. The encoder learned compact Gaussian representations that preserved important spatial structure. The differentiable renderer reconstructed clear images from these splats. The diffusion model then learned to generate and refine these latent representations in a stable and consistent manner. A key outcome of the work is the demonstration that structured representations can improve efficiency without significantly reducing visual quality. By operating in a lower-dimensional splat space, the model required less memory and computation than traditional pixel-space diffusion. At the same time, the grid of Gaussian primitives maintained spatial organization, helping preserve object shapes and over-

all scene layout during generation. Several directions can extend this work further. Training on larger and more diverse datasets is a natural next step. Using multiple object categories or full-scene images would test how well Gaussian splats capture broader visual variability. Scaling to higher resolutions is another promising direction. Since Gaussian primitives are not tied to a fixed pixel resolution, the same latent representation can be rendered at different output sizes. This creates opportunities for high-resolution synthesis without a proportional increase in latent dimensionality. The current framework relies on a fixed splat grid. Future research could explore adaptive or learned splat placements, where more primitives are assigned to complex regions and fewer to simpler areas. Conditional generation is another important extension. Incorporating class labels, text prompts, or semantic guidance could improve controllability while preserving the efficiency benefits of splat-based diffusion. Overall, the findings show that Gaussian splatting provides a practical connection between geometric representations and modern generative modeling. The approach offers a flexible and efficient foundation for continued research in structured latent diffusion and scalable image synthesis.

Code Availability

The code required to reproduce the experiments in this manuscript is available at https://github.com/ArchanGhosh/gaussian_splatting_diffusion.

References

- [1] Dor Bank, Noam Koenigstein, and Raja Giryes. Autoencoders, 2021. 5
- [2] Yuanhao Cai, He Zhang, Kai Zhang, Yixun Liang, Mengwei Ren, Fujun Luan, Qing Liu, Soo Ye Kim, Jianming Zhang, Zhifei Zhang, Yuqian Zhou, Yulun Zhang, Xiaokang Yang, Zhe Lin, and Alan Yuille. Baking gaussian splatting into diffusion denoiser for fast and scalable single-stage image-to-3d generation and reconstruction, 2025. 2
- [3] Guikun Chen and Wenguan Wang. A survey on 3d gaussian splatting, 2026. 1
- [4] Adam Coates, Honglak Lee, and Andrew Y. Ng. An analysis of single-layer networks in unsupervised feature learning. In *Proceedings of the Fourteenth International Conference on Artificial Intelligence and Statistics (AISTATS)*, pages 215–223, Fort Lauderdale, FL, USA, 2011. PMLR. 5, 6
- [5] Jean-Baptiste Cordonnier, Andreas Loukas, and Martin Jaggi. Multi-head attention: Collaborate instead of concatenate, 2021. 4
- [6] Jia Deng, Wei Dong, Richard Socher, Li-Jia Li, Kai Li, and Li Fei-Fei. Imagenet: A large-scale hierarchical image database. In *2009 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition*, pages 248–255, 2009. 5
- [7] Prafulla Dhariwal and Alex Nichol. Diffusion models beat gans on image synthesis, 2021. 1

- [8] Stefan Elfving, Eiji Uchibe, and Kenji Doya. Sigmoid-weighted linear units for neural network function approximation in reinforcement learning, 2017. 4
- [9] Ian J. Goodfellow, Jean Pouget-Abadie, Mehdi Mirza, Bing Xu, David Warde-Farley, Sherjil Ozair, Aaron Courville, and Yoshua Bengio. Generative adversarial networks, 2014. 1, 3
- [10] Kaiming He, Xiangyu Zhang, Shaoqing Ren, and Jian Sun. Deep residual learning for image recognition, 2015. 4
- [11] Jonathan Ho, Ajay Jain, and Pieter Abbeel. Denoising diffusion probabilistic models. *CoRR*, abs/2006.11239, 2020. 1, 6
- [12] Binbin Huang, Zehao Yu, Anpei Chen, Andreas Geiger, and Shenghua Gao. 2d gaussian splatting for geometrically accurate radiance fields. In *Special Interest Group on Computer Graphics and Interactive Techniques Conference Conference Papers*, page 1–11. ACM, 2024. 1
- [13] Peter J. Huber and Elvezio M. Ronchetti. *Robust Statistics*. John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, NJ, 2 edition, 2009. 7
- [14] Hiroharu Kato, Deniz Beker, Mihai Morariu, Takahiro Ando, Toru Matsuoka, Wadim Kehl, and Adrien Gaidon. Differentiable rendering: A survey, 2020. 3
- [15] Diederik P. Kingma and Jimmy Ba. Adam: A method for stochastic optimization, 2017. 5
- [16] Diederik P Kingma and Max Welling. Auto-encoding variational bayes, 2022. 1
- [17] Tejas D. Kulkarni, Will Whitney, Pushmeet Kohli, and Joshua B. Tenenbaum. Deep convolutional inverse graphics network, 2015. 1
- [18] Hongyu Li, Chaofeng Chen, Xiaoming Li, and Guangming Lu. 2d gaussian splatting with semantic alignment for image inpainting, 2025. 2
- [19] Maxime Oquab, Timothée Darcet, Théo Moutakanni, Huy Vo, Marc Szafraniec, Vasil Khalidov, Pierre Fernandez, Daniel Haziza, Francisco Massa, Alaaeldin El-Nouby, Mahmoud Assran, Nicolas Ballas, Wojciech Galuba, Russell Howes, Po-Yao Huang, Shang-Wen Li, Ishan Misra, Michael Rabbat, Vasu Sharma, Gabriel Synnaeve, Hu Xu, Hervé Jegou, Julien Mairal, Patrick Labatut, Armand Joulin, and Piotr Bojanowski. Dinov2: Learning robust visual features without supervision, 2024. 2
- [20] Razvan Pascanu, Tomas Mikolov, and Yoshua Bengio. On the difficulty of training recurrent neural networks, 2013. 4
- [21] Olaf Ronneberger, Philipp Fischer, and Thomas Brox. U-net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation, 2015. 2, 3, 4
- [22] Karen Simonyan and Andrew Zisserman. Very deep convolutional networks for large-scale image recognition, 2015. 2, 5
- [23] Ashish Vaswani, Noam Shazeer, Niki Parmar, Jakob Uszkoreit, Llion Jones, Aidan N. Gomez, Lukasz Kaiser, and Illia Polosukhin. Attention is all you need, 2023. 4
- [24] Sebastian Weiss and Derek Bradley. Gaussian billboards: Expressive 2d gaussian splatting with textures, 2024. 1
- [25] Zhaohu Xing, Liang Wan, Huazhu Fu, Guang Yang, and Lei Zhu. Diff-unet: A diffusion embedded network for volumetric segmentation, 2023. 2
- [26] Bing Xu, Naiyan Wang, Tianqi Chen, and Mu Li. Empirical evaluation of rectified activations in convolutional network, 2015. 2

A. Experimentation

All experiments were implemented using the PyTorch framework. Training and evaluation were conducted on two GPU platforms: an NVIDIA T4 and an NVIDIA RTX A5000. Due to the relatively short training cycles used during development, both GPUs were utilized to verify the consistency of results and to detect potential implementation or configuration issues during model design. Before conducting large-scale experiments, a controlled overfitting test was performed. Small-batch validation is common practice in many deep learning tasks. However, for diffusion-based models, such tests often provide limited insight due to the stochastic nature of the generation process. This challenge is further increased in the proposed framework because the Gaussian splat-based latent space introduces additional representational flexibility. To verify the feasibility of the approach, the model was trained to reconstruct a single target image. In this setting, the output closely matched the original image in both spatial structure and visual appearance. This experiment served as a sanity check, confirming that the encoder-renderer-diffusion pipeline is capable of accurately modeling and reconstructing image content under controlled conditions.

B. Architecture Testing

Figure 10. Sparsity Check

Figure 11. Interpolation check for Encoder

Tile-based rendering was used to improve computational efficiency and memory usage during Gaussian splat rendering. Since each splat mainly affects a local region of the image, processing the image in smaller spatial tiles avoids unnecessary computation over distant pixels with negligible influence. This localized processing reduces rendering cost while preserving full differentiability, enabling stable end-to-end training of the model. The experiments were conducted using images resized to a resolution of 128×128 pixels. The Gaussian splat representation was organized as a 32×32 grid, with four splats assigned to each grid cell. Each splat

was defined by nine parameters, resulting in a total of 36 latent channels per image. During encoder training, the Adam optimizer was used with an initial learning rate of 1×10^{-3} , which was reduced to 2×10^{-4} after 50 epochs to refine finer details. The autoencoder was trained for 150 epochs using a weighted reconstruction loss composed of 0.8 perceptual VGG loss and 0.2 mean squared error loss.

For diffusion training, the AdamW optimizer was used with a learning rate of 1×10^{-4} and a latent batch size of 32. The diffusion process used 500 timesteps with a linear beta schedule ranging from 1×10^{-4} to 0.02. The model was trained using a custom implementation of Huber loss for stable regression of latent values. Long-run training was performed for up to 50,000 epochs with periodic checkpointing and visual monitoring. Gaussian scales were initialized with a factor of 0.04 to encourage dense and localized splat coverage.

C. Post Training Tests

Figure 12. Noise Interpolation of Diffusion Model

Figure 13. Alpha Interpolation for Diffusion

Each Gaussian splat was defined using nine learnable parameters that describe its spatial and visual properties. Two parameters represented positional offsets within a grid cell, allowing splats to shift from fixed grid centers. Two additional parameters controlled anisotropic scaling along the x and y axes, enabling elliptical shapes. One parameter defined the rotation angle of the Gaussian. Three parameters represented RGB color values, and one parameter modeled opacity. Together, these parameters allowed each splat to capture both geometric structure and appearance within a localized image region.

Figure 14. Understanding Encoder Reconstruction

Figure 15. Fidelity Test of Generation

Figure 17. Similarity Crosscheck of Generation

Figure 18. Geometric Representation of Splats

Figure 16. Raw Latent Space

Figure 19. Uncurated Samples from a Noise Range